

Re-Assessment of the Strength and Deformation Behavior of Binary B2-ordered Iron Aluminides

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Abstract

1 Iron aluminides are potential candidates for structural applications at temperatures up to 700 °C. The
2 status of literature lacks a consistent and comprehensive understanding of the mechanical properties of
3 binary iron aluminides within the concentration range of B2-ordered FeAl with 30 to about 50 at.% Al.
4 The present study addresses this gap by systematically characterizing the composition- and temperature-
5 dependent mechanical behavior of a series of alloys with 30 to 53 at.% Al from room temperature (RT)
6 up to 700 °C. Particular emphasis was placed on achieving a consistently low impurity level and on
7 establishing comparable heat-treatment conditions to reduce the strengthening effect of point defects.
8 At RT, both hardness and yield strength exhibit a distinct trend after a vacancy minimizing heat
9 treatment at 400 °C for 120 h, first decreasing towards a minimum at 42 at.% and thereafter increasing
10 again to 53 at.% Al. RT compression tests reveal high strain hardening capability for alloys with < 50
11 at.% Al that diminishes as the Al content increases. Contrary to earlier reports, the increasing yield
12 strength with increasing temperature was only observed for alloys with 30 and 35 at.% Al. Post-
13 deformation SEM-BSE and SEM-EBSD analyses reveal uniform plastic deformation depending on
14 alloy composition below 400–600 °C, while kink band formation at higher temperatures significantly
15 reduces strain hardening. Dynamic recrystallization was observed at 700 °C in alloys with < 47 at.% Al.

Keywords

16 Iron aluminides, B2 ordered structure, compression testing, Vickers hardness, Nanoindentation,
17 deformation, strength

1. Introduction

18 Binary iron aluminides $\text{Fe}_x\text{Al}_{1-x}$ possess an outstanding corrosion and sulfidation resistance [1,2], a
19 high density-normalized Young's modulus and low density compared to Ni-based superalloys [2,3].
20 Since they are made of affordable elements [4], they are suitable for applications like coal
21 gasification [1], heat exchanger tubes, and protective coatings [3,5,6]. Binary body-centered cubic (bcc)-
22 based iron aluminides form different, disordered and ordered crystal structures depending on the Al
23 content, which determines strength, strain hardening capability, hardness and plastic deformability. At
24 room temperature (RT) [2], the $A2$ -disordered crystal structure forms up to 18 at.% Al, the $D0_3$ -ordered
25 structure appears between 18 and 35 at.% Al, and the $B2$ -ordered crystal structure forms at Al contents
26 up to 50 at.% Al. For high-temperature application, $B2$ -ordered iron aluminides between 35 and 50 at.%
27 Al are of particular interest as they are exceptionally oxidation and sulfidation resistant [1,2].

28 The RT strength of iron aluminides is rather low (~ 300 MPa for up to 48 at.% Al [7]) and strongly
29 depends on the Al content [8] as well as on point defects like impurity solute atoms and vacancies [7].
30 The temperature-dependent yield strength σ_y of iron aluminides, which is divided into four regions, is
31 shown in Figure 1 with:

- 32 - Region I: Strength decreases with increasing temperature by thermal activation of dislocation
33 motion [11,12]
- 34 - Region II: Strength is dependent on the intrinsic lattice resistance
- 35 - YSA Region ("Yield strength anomaly"): σ_y can increase with increasing temperature for alloys
36 with < 47 at.% Al by more than 100 MPa compared to σ_y at RT (YS peak) [2,10,13–16]
- 37 - Region III: A drop of σ_y occurs due to the onset of diffusion-controlled plastic deformation [12]

Figure 1: Schematic temperature dependence of σ_y and σ_f of $B2$ -ordered iron aluminides adopted from Refs. [2,9,10]. The transition temperatures between two regions are visualized with yellow areas.

38 Mechanical strength of iron aluminides in the regions I, II and the YS peak is sensitive to the
39 concentration of vacancies [16], which in turn is influenced by the heat treatment and cooling
40 conditions [17]. Retained vacancies from heat treatment at high temperatures, for example 1000 $^{\circ}\text{C}$, raise
41 σ_y within the regions I, II and YSA [2]. Observation of the YS peak is dependent on a vacancy-reducing
42 heat treatment at 400 $^{\circ}\text{C}$. Thermally generated vacancies at temperatures below the YS peak are

43 considered to be the reason for the increase of σ_y . They exhibit a low formation (~ 1 eV) and high
44 migration enthalpy (up to 2.3 eV) [9,10]. The low temperature heat treatment at 400 °C is intended to
45 remove these excess vacancies, enabling “close to thermodynamic equilibrium conditions” [17,18].
46 Durations vary in the range of 100–120 h across different literature reports [9,17,19,20]. A YS peak has
47 been reported for example for 120 h in Ref. [9].

48 The determination of the temperature-dependent σ_y as the onset of macroscopic plastic deformation can
49 be obstructed in the case of brittle materials by premature normal fracture (cleavage) in tension. To
50 circumvent the cleavage and premature failure of a specimen, compression tests can be utilized. As
51 illustrated in Figure 1, the fracture stress σ_f is less sensitive to a temperature increase, just following the
52 trend of elastic stiffness. For brittle materials, it may be lower than the yield strength σ_y , specifically at
53 low test temperatures. Thus, a transition from brittle to ductile material behavior is observed, which
54 defines the so-called brittle-to-ductile transition temperature (BDTT) [21]. Consequently, σ_y is not
55 directly accessible in tensile tests at temperatures below BDTT, as is for *B2*-ordered iron aluminides,
56 because they suffer from weak grain boundary cohesion [22,23] and inherent brittleness [24]. Notably,
57 the BDTT for binary *B2*-ordered iron aluminides with up to 45 at.% Al has only been determined in
58 four-point bending tests for alloys after casting [8], where a continuous increase with increasing Al-
59 content up to 42 at.% Al and a strong increase for higher Al-concentrations was found.

60 Interpreting temperature-dependent mechanical properties in iron aluminides can be challenging when
61 the distinction between σ_y and σ_f in tension is not made explicit in the literature, specifically when the
62 test temperature is close to or below BDTT. In several reports, the YS peak is associated with stress
63 values that may potentially reflect σ_f rather than the intrinsic onset of plasticity. For the temperature
64 range in which the YSA is discussed, stress–strain curves are often not available, e.g. in Refs. [10,13–
65 16], which makes it difficult to confirm yielding. This view is consistent with the fracture surfaces
66 described in Refs. [13,15,16,25–39], which frequently exhibit brittle characteristics. Together, the
67 observations raise the possibility that some reported stresses capture fracture limits rather than yield
68 strengths. Accordingly, the mechanistic understanding of the YS peak and the temperature dependence
69 of strength in these alloys remains partially incomplete. In addition, the mesoscopic microstructural
70 changes induced by plastic deformation have been less systematically characterized.

71 The present study aims at generating appropriate datasets on σ_y with the respective stress-strain curves,
72 the analysis thereof and the microstructure after deformation over the entire Al concentration range of
73 *B2*-ordered iron aluminides. Specifically, it is focused on (i) keeping consistent impurity concentrations
74 between the different alloys and (ii) establishing comparable, defect-lean microstructural conditions by
75 appropriate heat treatments. By utilizing the combination of compression tests, Vickers hardness
76 measurements and nanoindentation experiments on *B2*-ordered iron aluminides cast from the same batch
77 of raw materials, a comprehensive overview over the mechanical properties on the meso- and
78 macroscale is provided. The experimental approach aims to clarify the following scientific questions:

- 79 1. How do mechanical properties, such as hardness, yield strength and strain hardening at RT up
80 to 700 °C, of single-phase, *B2*-ordered FeAl alloys with Al concentrations between 30 and
81 53 at.% Al depend on temperature and composition?
- 82 2. What changes occur in the mesoscale microstructure depending on test temperature and alloy
83 composition?
- 84 3. How does the temperature-dependent evolution of the mesoscale microstructure correlate with
85 the mechanical properties of the alloys?

2. Materials and Experimental Methodology

86 The alloys used in this study with nominal compositions of 30, 35, 42, 47, 50 and 53 at.% Al were
87 produced in a vacuum induction furnace (Balzers and Co., Bad Schönborn, Germany) from pure Fe
88 (99.9 % purity) and Al (99.95 % purity) under Ar and cast into rectangular Cu molds with dimensions
89 of $(200 \cdot 40 \cdot 180)$ mm³. For all alloys, the same raw materials were used to keep the impurity contents
90 comparable among the alloys.

91 The ingots were cut to cuboid testing samples with the nominal size of $(3 \cdot 3 \cdot 5)$ mm³ by utilizing a
92 wire electric discharge machine (EDM), model BA24 supplied by Mitsubishi Electric
93 Corporation (Tokyo, Japan). After EDM processing, the samples were ground to grit P1000 SiC paper
94 to remove the oxidized surface layer followed by ultrasonic cleaning in ethanol. For the two-stage heat
95 treatment process, the compression testing samples were encapsulated into fused silica ampoules, which
96 were evacuated and back-filled with Ar of 99.996 % purity for five times. To prevent Si diffusion from
97 the fused silica into the specimens during heat treatment [40], the samples were wrapped in thin Mo-foil
98 (ThermoFisher Scientific, Waltham Massachusetts, USA) before encapsulation. The heat treatment
99 consisted of homogenization at 1000 °C ($0.73 \dots 0.93 \cdot T_S$, solidus temperature T_S) for 48 h (except for
100 Fe-53Al with 168 h) with subsequent rapid cooling by dropping the ampoules into water. This procedure
101 is followed by a low temperature heat treatment at 400 °C for 120 h also in ampoules to reduce excess
102 vacancies [9] and again subsequent rapid cooling. A laboratory chamber furnace CWF1300 by Carbolite
103 Gero GmbH & Co. KG (Neuhausen, Germany) was used for all heat treatments. The oxide scale on the
104 samples was removed by grinding to P1000 SiC paper.

105 For microstructural investigations, a standard metallographic grinding and polishing procedure was
106 applied. The sample surfaces were first ground with SiC paper to grit P4000. Subsequently, mechanical
107 polishing was carried out utilizing a non-crystallizing oxide polishing suspension with pH = 7, particle
108 size 50 nm (OP-S, Sommer Diamant Abrasive GmbH, Euenheim, Germany). This step was followed by
109 chemo-mechanical polishing with a non-crystallizing oxide polishing suspension with pH = 9.8, particle
110 size 40 nm (OP-S, Struers ApS, Ballerup, Denmark) to further remove the deformed layer after grinding.
111 Finally, chemo-mechanical vibratory polishing was applied for 8 h utilizing a non-crystallizing oxide
112 polishing suspension with pH = 9.8 (OP-S NonDry, Struers ApS, Ballerup, Denmark). For
113 nanoindentation, the samples were mechanically polished up to 1 μm diamond suspension, followed by
114 electropolishing using A2 electrolyte (Struers ApS, Ballerup, Denmark).

115 The crystal structure of all alloys was determined by X-ray diffraction (XRD) with a D2 Phaser device
116 supplied by Bruker Corporation (MA, USA). The chemical composition was determined in the as-cast
117 condition by means of inductively coupled plasma optical emission spectroscopy (ICP-OES) with an
118 iCAP 7600 DUO analyzer (ThermoFisher Scientific, Waltham Massachusetts, USA), carrier gas hot
119 extraction (CGHE) and combustion analysis (CA) with TC 600 and CS 600 devices, both supplied by
120 LECO (St. Joseph, Michigan, USA). Backscattered electron (SEM-BSE) and secondary electron
121 imaging (SEM-SE) were performed utilizing a Leo 1530 field emission gun scanning electron
122 microscope (SEM, Carl Zeiss AG, Oberkochen, Germany). SEM-BSE imaging was used for obtaining
123 information about homogeneity by using atomic number contrast. In addition, SEM-SE contrast imaging
124 was used for identification of topographic features such as pores and cracks. The acceleration voltage
125 was set to 20 kV in all cases. Mesoscale deformation mechanisms were investigated by using an Auriga
126 60 focused ion beam field emission gun SEM (Carl Zeiss AG, Oberkochen, Germany) equipped with
127 an EDAX DigiView electron backscatter diffraction system (EBSD, AMETEK Inc., Berwyn, USA).
128 Data were acquired on an area of $(800 \cdot 800)$ μm² in size at a step size of 2 μm. EBSD data was evaluated
129 with MTEX [41] in MATLAB.

130 Quasi-static compression tests were performed on a Z100 universal testing machine with an electro-
 131 mechanical drive supplied by ZwickRoell GmbH & Co. KG (Ulm, Germany) equipped with a three-
 132 zone vacuum furnace and temperature controller by Maytec GmbH (Singen, Germany). The heating rate
 133 was 10 K/min and the sample was held at the testing temperature for 30 min prior to testing. The initial
 134 engineering strain rate $\dot{\epsilon}$ was set to 10^{-4} s^{-1} . Hexagonal BN was used as a lubricant to reduce friction
 135 forces between samples' faces and punches. The temperature of the sample was measured during testing
 136 with a type S thermocouple, which was applied to the center of the sample. The atmospheric pressure
 137 inside the furnace was kept lower than $1 \cdot 10^{-4}$ mbar during all tests. For each temperature step, three
 138 compression tests were conducted to check reproducibility of test data.

139 The hardness of the alloys was evaluated by using a Q10A+ semi-automatic Vickers hardness (HV)
 140 indenter from ATM Qness GmbH (Mammelzen, Germany) with a load of 1kg (HV1). A minimum
 141 number of ten indents within a random selection of grains were evaluated for statistical reasons. The
 142 minimum distance between two indents were at least three times the largest diagonal of the indents, the
 143 distance to the sample edges were at least six times the largest diagonal, according to DIN EN ISO 6507-
 144 1:2024 [42]. Nanoindentation was performed on different grains of the specimens with a distance of at
 145 least 30 μm from one indent to another (more than 25 times the maximum indentation depth) using a
 146 G200 nanoindenter by KLA Corporation (Milpitas, CA, USA). A diamond Berkovich indenter was used
 147 with a maximum indentation depth of 1 μm at a constant strain rate of 0.02 s^{-1} . Nine indents were
 148 performed on each grain. The analysis developed by Oliver and Pharr [43,44] was used to determine the
 149 nanohardness.

3. Results

3.1 Chemical Analysis and Initial Microstructure

150 The chemical composition of all alloys after casting was verified using ICP-OES, CGHE and CA. The
 151 results presented in Table 1 show that the actual alloy compositions closely align with the desired ones.
 152 Additionally, impurity levels are consistently low across the different alloys, which has previously been
 153 reported for this processing route in Ref. [14]. N and S were below the detection limit.

Table 1: Chemical composition of the investigated alloys by ICP-OES (Al, Mn, Si) and CGHE (O, N) and CA (C, S). Fe is balanced.

Desired Al at.%	Al at.%	Al wt.%	Mn wt.ppm	Si wt.ppm	O wt.ppm	N wt.ppm	C wt.ppm	S wt.ppm
30	30.1 ± 0.7	17 ± 0.4	347 ± 10	69 ± 20	12 ± 30	< 1	65 ± 15	< 20
35	34.8 ± 0.9	20.3 ± 0.5	332 ± 10	117 ± 20	99 ± 30	< 1	55 ± 15	< 20
42	41.4 ± 1.2	25.1 ± 0.7	310 ± 10	122 ± 20	163 ± 30	< 1	9 ± 15	< 20
47	46.6 ± 1.3	29.5 ± 0.8	323 ± 10	140 ± 20	95 ± 30	< 1	46 ± 15	< 20
50	49.9 ± 1.3	32 ± 0.8	311 ± 10	138 ± 20	14 ± 30	< 1	52 ± 15	< 20
53	52.4 ± 1.4	34.4 ± 0.9	276 ± 10	151 ± 20	65 ± 30	< 1	31 ± 15	< 20

154 To investigate the microstructure following the homogenization at 1000 °C and subsequent low-
 155 temperature heat treatment at 400 °C, SEM-BSE micrographs were recorded and XRD measurements
 156 were conducted. Representative micrographs for all alloys are shown in Figure 2, while the XRD data
 157 are provided in the Supplementary Material (Figure S1).

Figure 2: The microstructure of iron aluminides after heat treatment at 1000 °C for 48 h (Fe-53Al: 168 h) and 400 °C for 120 h: a) Fe-30Al, b) Fe-35Al, c) Fe-42Al, d) Fe-47Al, e) Fe-50Al, f) Fe-53Al. The scale bar is the same for all images. Fe-53Al shows artefacts from preparation.

158 All alloys exhibit grain sizes in the range of 200–300 μm. The micrographs indicate that, apart from Fe-
 159 53Al, all alloys possess a homogeneous, single-phase microstructure at the micrometer scale. Based on
 160 the applied heat treatment at 400 °C and the phase diagram reported in Ref. [2], Fe-30Al is D0₃-ordered,
 161 while Fe-35Al, Fe-42Al, Fe-47Al, and Fe-50Al are single-phase B2-ordered. In the case of Fe-53Al, a
 162 secondary FeAl₂ phase [2] is observed as lenticular features both within grains and along grain
 163 boundaries after 400 °C/120 h (Supplementary Material Figure S2 for more details).

3.2 Mechanical Properties

3.2.1 Hardness tests

164 The hardness is an indicator for vacancies retained in the alloys, if grain size and other microstructural
 165 parameters remain constant. Thermal vacancies follow an Arrhenius-like relationship with
 166 temperature [45,46]. The Vickers hardness (HV) at RT after the homogenization at 1000 °C (HT) for
 167 48 h (single-phase Fe-53Al: 168 h, shown in Supplementary Material Figure S3) is presented in Figure
 168 3.

Figure 3: HV as a function of alloy composition after a heat treatment at 1000 °C for 48 h (Fe-53Al: 168 h). For comparison, data from Ref. [17] are plotted as black hexagons. A dotted line is used as a guideline to the eyes.

169 For samples with this heat treatment, the HV continuously increases with increasing Al content, being
 170 consistent with the data published in Ref. [17], included in Figure 3 for comparison. In order to reduce
 171 the amount of thermal vacancies present in the alloys after HT as much as possible [17], the alloys
 172 discussed here were subjected to a heat treatment at 400 °C for 120 h. The results are presented in Figure
 173 4.

Figure 4: HV and NH as a function of alloy composition after a heat treatment at 400 °C for 120 h. For comparison, data from Ref. [17] are plotted as black symbols. Dashed and dotted lines are used as a guideline to the eyes.

174 After the additional heat treatment at 400 °C, the HV of Fe-30Al does not change in comparison to HT
 175 and remains at (2.7 ± 0.1) GPa. As also no change in constituting phases nor in grain size was observed
 176 for this alloy, it can be concluded that there is no or a negligible change in point defect concentration.
 177 For all other alloys, the hardness after the heat treatment at 400 °C for 120 h is significantly lower
 178 compared to HT. Fe-42Al shows the lowest HV among the alloys tested. By further increasing the Al
 179 content, the hardness increases again. The results obtained from nanohardness (NH) measurements show
 180 the same trend as HV for 400 °C after 120 h but are shifted to higher values because of the indentation
 181 size effect [47].

3.2.1 Compression tests

182 To investigate the yield strength and strain hardening behavior, compression tests were performed.
 183 Representative true stress – true strain curves for the alloys deformed at RT after a heat treatment at
 184 400 °C for 120 h are presented in Figure 5a. All data from the compression tests are available via Zenodo
 185 under CC BY-SA 4.0 license .

186 The compression tests for the alloys with < 50 at.% Al content have been deliberately interrupted at $(15$
 187 $\pm 1)$ % true strain, as marked by arrows, whereas the samples for Fe-50Al and Fe-53Al failed after
 188 reaching true strains of (15 ± 1) % and (8 ± 1) %, respectively. The room-temperature strain hardening
 189 behavior of the alloys is plotted in Figure 5b as Kocks-Mecking plots by showing true strain hardening
 190 $d\sigma_t/d\varepsilon_t$ as a function of true stress σ_t [48]. If there are no other crack-initiating mechanisms active, the
 191 corresponding strain, where $d\sigma_t/d\varepsilon_t = \sigma_t$ is fulfilled, marks the upper limit of strain that the material
 192 can achieve via uniform plastic deformation *in tension* as the engineering relevant loading condition.
 193 Thus, compression tests serve as a first, relevant screening criterion for potential tensile ductility. The
 194 alloys with < 50 at.% Al have the potential to uniformly deform up to minimum 15 % true strain. In
 195 contrast, the alloys with 50 and 53 at.% Al suffer from low strain hardening, showing a similar behavior

196 to what has been published in Ref. [49]. The strain for Fe-47Al, where the $d\sigma_t/d\varepsilon_t = \sigma_t$ criterion is met,
 197 is (15 ± 1) % true strain (marked with a red dot in the figure). Fe-50Al and Fe-53Al fulfill the $d\sigma_t/d\varepsilon_t =$
 198 σ_t criterion at true strains of (13 ± 1) % and (8 ± 1) %, respectively.

Figure 5: a) Representative (selected) true stress – true strain curves for the alloys measured at RT after heat treatment at 400 °C for 120 h. Crosses mark tests with failed samples. The other tests were interrupted at $\varepsilon_t = (15 \pm 1)$ %, indicated by arrows. The initial engineering strain rate $\dot{\varepsilon}$ was set to 10^{-4} s^{-1} . b) Kocks-Mecking plots derived from the tests shown in a). Red dots mark where $\sigma_t = \frac{d\sigma_t}{d\varepsilon_t}$ is met.

199 The RT 1 % and 5 % offset yield strengths (R_{p1} and R_{p5}) were determined for all alloys and are
 200 displayed in Figure 6a. R_{p1} was used to avoid scatter by localization of plastic deformation in the early
 201 stages of compression [50].

202 Given the extent of plastic deformation and strain hardening during hardness measurements, a direct
 203 transformation into the initial yield strength is not possible. While the flow stress at 8 % plastic strain
 204 can be employed for correlating hardness and strength [51], Fe-53Al exhibited premature failure prior
 205 to reaching this strain level. Consequently, the flow stress at 5% true strain was utilized in Figure 6b to
 206 remain consistent among all alloys [52]. The resulting correlation between R_{p5} and HV (both for 400 °C
 207 for 120 h) is $R_{p5} = 0.26 \cdot HV$, (adjusted coefficient of confidence $R_{adj}^2 = 0.99$) and the correlation
 208 between R_{p5} and NH is $R_{p5} = 0.20 \cdot H$ ($R_{adj}^2 = 0.98$). Both correlations are shown in the
 209 Supplementary Material in Figures S4 and S5.

Figure 6: a) R_{p1} and R_{p5} at room-temperature as function of composition (closed squares for R_{p1} , open squares for R_{p5}). b) Comparison of true strain hardening $\frac{d\sigma_t}{d\varepsilon_t}$ as slope between $\varepsilon_t = 1\%$ and 1.5% plastic strain. The black squares are data taken from Ref. [53]. Error bars are smaller than the symbol size. Trendlines are shown in both figures as guidelines to the eyes.

210 The strain hardening coefficient for each alloy has been determined in this work as slopes taken from
 211 the true stress – true strain curves between 1% and 1.5% plastic strain to remain consistent with
 212 Ref. [53]. A steady increase with increasing Al-content is found between 30 and 50 at.% Al, whereas a
 213 steep increase is found at 53 at.% Al. A detailed discussion of this is provided in Section 4.

214 For the investigation of the high temperature behavior of the alloys, compression tests have been carried
 215 out up to $700\text{ }^\circ\text{C}$. Representative true stress – true strain curves for Fe-35Al and Fe-50Al are shown in
 216 Figure 7a and Figure 8a alongside Kocks-Mecking plots; for the other investigated alloys, the reader is
 217 referred to the Supplementary Material (Figures S6-S9).

Figure 7: a) Representative (selected) true stress – true strain curves for Fe-35Al at different temperatures. The tests were interrupted at $\varepsilon_t = (15 \pm 1)\%$, indicated by arrows. The initial engineering strain rate $\dot{\varepsilon}$ was set to 10^{-4} s^{-1} . b) Kocks-Mecking plots for the Fe-35Al deformed at different temperatures.

218 The stress-strain curves of Fe-35Al reveal strain hardening at temperatures up to $500\text{ }^\circ\text{C}$, which is
 219 representative for the alloys up to 47 at.% Al. At $600\text{ }^\circ\text{C}$, a maximum in the stress-strain curve is
 220 observed, indicating the onset of dynamic recovery or recrystallization [54]. Section 3.3 provides the
 221 supporting evidence. At $700\text{ }^\circ\text{C}$, the curve flattens and the alloy does not show any strain hardening.
 222 The strain where $d\sigma_t/d\varepsilon_t = \sigma_t$ is fulfilled is not reached for the alloy deformed at temperatures below
 223 $500\text{ }^\circ\text{C}$, but it is reached at a true strain of $(13 \pm 1)\%$ for deformation at $500\text{ }^\circ\text{C}$ and at $(3 \pm 1)\%$ for
 224 deformation at $600\text{ }^\circ\text{C}$ and $700\text{ }^\circ\text{C}$, respectively. The red dots in Figure 7b mark the points where the

225 criterion is fulfilled. As the deformation at temperatures of 500 °C ($0.46 \cdot T_S$) and above lie within the
 226 creep region, which usually starts at $\sim 0.4 \cdot T_S$ [55], the alloys with < 47 at.% Al deform homogeneously.

Figure 8: a) Representative (selected) true stress – true strain curves for Fe-50Al at different temperatures. The test at RT failed at $\epsilon_t = (15 \pm 1) \%$, indicated by a cross. All other tests were interrupted at $\epsilon_t = (15 \pm 1) \%$, indicated by arrows. The initial engineering strain rate $\dot{\epsilon}$ was set to 10^{-4} s^{-1} . b) Kocks-Mecking plots for the Fe-50Al deformed at different temperatures.

227 For Fe-50Al, the temperature-dependent behavior is different. Strain hardening is observed for RT and
 228 400 °C, but to a lesser extent than for Fe-35Al as intergranular cracks are formed during deformation
 229 (displayed in Figure 11, see Section 3.3). This is discussed in more detail in chapter 0. At higher
 230 temperatures, the strain hardening drops substantially. No maxima in the stress-strain curves are found,
 231 which indicate a dominant dislocation strengthening over dynamic recovery during deformation. The
 232 samples fail at RT at a maximum strain of $(15 \pm 1) \%$. The strain where $d\sigma_t/d\epsilon_t = \sigma_t$ is fulfilled (red
 233 dots in Figure 8b) is even lower at a true strain of 13 %. When deforming the alloy at higher
 234 temperatures, the $d\sigma_t/d\epsilon_t = \sigma_t$ criterion is reached at true strains of $(10 \pm 1) \%$ at 400 °C, $(4 \pm 1) \%$ at
 235 500 °C and only $(2 \pm 1) \%$ at 600 °C and 700 °C, respectively. Again, as the deformation at temperatures
 236 of 500 °C ($0.51 \cdot T_S$) and above lie within the creep region with $> 0.4 \cdot T_S$ [55].

Figure 9: The temperature and composition-dependent R_{p1} of the investigated iron aluminides.

237 Figure 9 displays the temperature-dependent R_{p1} for all alloys after the heat treatment at 400 °C for
 238 120 h between RT and 700 °C. Assessing Figure 9 against the temperature-dependent strength displayed

239 in Figure 1, we can divide the temperature-dependent strength into three (Fe-30Al and Fe-35Al: four)
 240 different regions. The low-temperature regime displayed in Figure 1 with a low thermal contribution for
 241 overcoming the energy barrier against dislocation motion, is below the temperature range in the current
 242 investigation. Instead, RT is already within the temperature of the plateau region (indicated as region II
 243 in Figure 1), which starts at $\sim 0.2 \cdot T_S$ [55] (Fe-30Al: $0.17 \cdot T_S$, Fe-53Al: $0.21 \cdot T_S$). This plateau region
 244 extends to 400 °C ($0.39 \cdot T_S$, Fe-30Al and $0.44 \cdot T_S$, Fe-50Al) or 500 °C ($0.46 \cdot T_S$, Fe-35Al). The
 245 strength of Fe-30Al changes from $R_{p1} = (375 \pm 30)$ MPa at RT, (314 ± 34) MPa at 400 °C to
 246 (351 ± 17) MPa at 500 °C, indicating the YSA region (see Figure 1). For Fe-35Al, the strength changes
 247 from $R_{p1} = (292 \pm 12)$ MPa at RT to (282 ± 18) MPa at 400 °C, (303 ± 14) MPa at 500 °C and
 248 (311 ± 11) MPa at 600 °C. A significant drop of strength (i.e., region III in Figure 1) for all alloys is
 249 observed at temperatures of 400–600 °C due to the onset of diffusion-controlled creep deformation at
 250 quasi-static strain rates.

3.3 Microstructure after Deformation

251 To investigate the deformation behavior, micrographs by means of SEM-BSE were taken for all alloys
 252 at all temperatures discussed above after deformation to a true strain of (15 ± 1) %. Figure 10 shows the
 253 microstructure of Fe-35Al as a representative low-Al alloy, while Figure 11 presents Fe-50Al as a
 254 representative high-Al alloy. The microstructure of the other alloys investigated are presented in the
 255 Supplementary Material in Figures S10-S13. Fe-35Al and Fe-50Al show localized plastic deformation
 256 up to temperatures of 600 °C. At 600 °C, Fe-35Al shows lenticular features within the grains, which are
 257 perpendicular to each other, indicating the activation of multiple slip systems. The initial part of the true
 258 stress – true strain curve for Fe-35Al shows the onset of dynamic recrystallization at 700 °C as new
 259 grains are formed as necklace structure at the former grain boundaries, which is not found for Fe-50Al.
 260 In addition, Fe-50Al shows the formation of intergranular cracks, which is observed up to a testing
 261 temperature of 700 °C.

Figure 10: The microstructure of Fe-35Al after deformation to $\epsilon_t = (15 \pm 1)$ % at different temperatures: a) RT, b) 400°C ($0.40 \cdot T_S$), c) 500°C ($0.46 \cdot T_S$), d) 600°C ($0.52 \cdot T_S$), and e) 700°C ($0.57 \cdot T_S$). The scale bar is the same for all images. The compression direction is horizontal.

Figure 11: The microstructure of Fe-50Al after deformation to $\epsilon_t = (15 \pm 1) \%$ at different temperatures: a) RT, b) 400°C ($0.44 \cdot T_S$), c) 500°C ($0.51 \cdot T_S$), d) 600°C ($0.58 \cdot T_S$), and e) 700°C ($0.65 \cdot T_S$). The scale bar is the same for all images. The compression direction is horizontal.

262 The deformation bands seen in the SEM-BSE micrographs show a change in contrast, which indicates
 263 a change in orientation. These bands could therefore be kink bands (KBs), which were further
 264 investigated by EBSD. Figure 12a (left) displays the inverse pole figure (IPF) map with respect to the
 265 compression direction of the deformed microstructure of Fe-35Al with a true strain of $(15 \pm 1) \%$ at
 266 600 °C. Within some grains, KBs of different orientation are found, highlighted by black arrows.

Figure 12: Properties of KBs for Fe-35Al after deformation at 600 °C. a) region of interest (ROI) as an orientation map (left) with respect to compression direction (the color code of orientations corresponds to the IPF in the inset in the left upper corner) and kernel average misorientation (KAM) map of the identical area (right). Black arrows highlight KBs. b) Misorientation angle distribution along the boundary of an individual kink band highlighted by the red polygon in a). c) Relative frequency distribution of misorientation angles (histogram) from b). A Gauss fit is plotted as line in the diagram. d) Orientation distribution of rotation axes determined from b) presented as colored map in an IPF. e) Stereographic projections from the orientations obtained in a) including the possible slip planes (kink band interface normal vectors) highlighted as black lines. Eulerian angles in Bunge notation.

267 The KAM map presented in Figure 12a (right) visualizes the local misorientation at the boundaries of
 268 the KBs. One individual band was picked for further analysis, highlighted by a red polygon in the
 269 KAM map. Varying shades of red color along the kink band boundaries reveal a varying
 270 misorientation, which is also displayed in Figure 12b in the magnified image of the band. The color-
 271 coded misorientation angle along the kink band boundary revealed misorientation angles between 9°
 272 and 21°. The relative frequency distribution of these angles (bin size of 3°) of this kink band is plotted
 273 in Figure 12c. For fitting the data with a Gauss curve, the frequency maximum was found at 13.5° and
 274 a full width at half maximum (FWHM) of 5.6° ($R_{adj}^2 = 0.87$). The distribution of rotation axes (Figure
 275 12d) within the individual band as depicted in the IPF map of Figure 12b reveals a maximum in the
 276 [001]-direction. For identifying the most probable slip plane, the KBs were analyzed similar to the
 277 procedure described in Ref. [56]. The intersections of the boundaries of these KBs with the surface are

278 found at angles close to $(80 \pm 3)^\circ$ with respect to the compression direction. The corresponding plane
279 normal can be constructed by an in-plane rotation of 90° , if the KBs extend only in out-of-plane
280 direction (the direction of view). As already described in Ref. [57], the observed features could
281 possess varying morphologies as the orientation map is only a 2D section of the deformed sample.
282 Hence, to determine the possible slip plane, a straight line must be added to the stereographic
283 projection as no information about the exact orientation of the plane is obtained by EBSD analysis.
284 Possible slip planes are directions which lie within the given range of $(10^\circ \pm 3^\circ)$ with respect to the
285 compression direction in the stereographic projection. This analysis has been carried out for different
286 KBs seen in Figure 12a (left), additional data can be found in the Supplementary Material in Figures
287 S14 and S15. For the different KBs, the misorientation with respect to the surrounding grains ranges
288 from 8° to 16.5° . Neither a uniform rotation axis nor a uniform slip system has been found for the
289 features in differently orientated grains.

4. Discussion

290 The manufacturing of samples made of binary iron aluminides is crucial when it comes to the assessment
291 of mechanical properties, as it affects the chemical homogeneity and impurity contents. The effects of
292 (i) accuracy of the chemical composition as well as (ii) chemical inhomogeneity following synthesis can
293 be estimated when evaluating the RT hardness (Figure 4) and σ_y (Figure 6) of chemically homogenous
294 Fe-Al alloys. A variation of the Al content by a few atomic percents leads to a significant change in
295 hardness and strength, especially for alloys which contain > 42 at.% Al, for example a spread of 1.5 GPa
296 in HV and 460 MPa in σ_y in Fe-(47 \pm 3)Al, respectively. (i) With respect to the accuracy of the actual
297 composition (in comparison to the desired composition), some studies from literature do not disclose
298 experimental verification which needs to be considered in comparisons [10,13,15,16]. In the present
299 study, the maximum experimentally verified deviations of -0.6 at.% Al (Fe-42Al and Fe-53Al) are well
300 below the standard deviations (~ 1 at.%) of the chemical composition determination by ICP-OES and
301 can be considered as minor. The impurity levels are small and the slight variations among the alloys
302 investigated in this study are considered negligible for the trends observed for hardness and strength as
303 a function of Al concentration. (ii) Chemical homogeneity needs to be considered for example when
304 assessing Ref. [8] dealing with the composition-depending BDTT which was obtained on the as-cast
305 condition without further homogenization treatment. Other studies used for the comparative assessment
306 of strength and strain hardening data presented in this study, rely on homogenization treatments at
307 temperatures between 850 [16] and 1200 °C [10,13–15,17]. However, durations are either undefined
308 [15] or vary between 10 min and 10 h [10,13,14,16,17]. The microstructural investigations by SEM-
309 BSE (Figure 2 and Figure S1, SEM-EDS not shown here) experimentally prove the chemical
310 homogeneity on the micrometer scale of the alloys synthesized in this study with 1000 °C/48 h
311 homogenization treatment (Fe-53Al for 168 h at the same temperature, Figure S3).

312 Apart from the chemical composition, grain size might affect the assessment of mechanical properties,
313 for example with respect to strength and hardness by grain boundary strengthening or with respect to
314 fracture stresses by weak grain boundaries in experimental studies from literature. The grain sizes after
315 the processing of the alloys were mostly reported to be in the range of 200–400 μm in literature [13,15–
316 17] similar to the grain sizes obtained in the present study. Thus, these studies are comparable with the
317 present one. Compared to the sample size, these large grain sizes contribute to the scatter obtained for
318 the strength data shown in Figure 6 and Figure 9 by favorable orientation of selected grains in some
319 specimens [58]. This statistical variation upon testing of multiple samples per condition is deliberately
320 characterized by the uncertainty ranges and bands included in the Figures. Considering the anticipated
321 dependencies (composition and temperature dependence), the scatter is small. Across all length scales,
322 macroscopic testing, hardness and nanohardness yield consistent results. The number of samples tested

323 as well as scatter ranges often remain undisclosed in literature, for example Refs. [10,13–16], which
324 precludes a deeper assessment of this factor in comparison to literature.

325 The hardness and strength of binary iron aluminides is significantly influenced by the point-defect
326 concentration [45]. Immediately after the completion of the homogenization treatment at 1000 °C, high
327 point defect concentration and, thus, high hardness is observed [45]. It is to be noted that further
328 mechanical characterization is impossible in this processing condition even by compression tests due to
329 the brittleness obtained for all alloys (fracture within the elastic range at low strains and with enormous
330 scatter of fracture stress, not shown here). To assess the materials' properties, a point-defect reducing
331 heat treatment at 400 °C for 120 h has been performed, leading to a lower hardness for all tested alloys.
332 Figure 3 and Figure 4 present the Vickers hardness after homogenization at 1000 °C and subsequent
333 aging at 400 °C, respectively, along with data from Ref. [17]. The trend of Vickers hardness obtained
334 after homogenization at 1000 °C and aging at 400 °C is consistent with the results reported in Ref. [17],
335 despite slight differences in the duration of the thermal treatments (homogenization at 1000 °C/0.5 h
336 [17] vs. 48 h in the present study and 400 °C/118 h [17] vs. 120 h, respectively). The trends observed in
337 HV, NH, and σ_y in the present study reveal a local minimum at 42 at.% Al, followed by a pronounced
338 increase for higher Al concentrations. The same trend for the RT strength was presented in Refs. [13–
339 16]. In Ref. [14], where the lowest strength was observed at 40 and 45 at.% Al, the absence of
340 intermediate compositions precluded precise identification of the minimum. σ_y at RT obtained in the
341 present study is comparable to the strength reported in Ref. [14] for 40–52 at.% Al, both in terms of
342 magnitude and composition dependence. The alloys in Ref. [14] were processed via a similar route and
343 with similar impurity contents. Also, the absolute strengths reported in Refs. [13,15,16] match those in
344 the present study up to an Al-content of 46 at.% ranging from 250 to 320 MPa. However, at higher Al-
345 contents, specifically at 48 at.% and 50 at.% Al, deviations were found. The strength at RT was reported
346 to be around 300 MPa at 48 at.% Al (vs. Fe-47Al with 450 MPa), and 1 GPa at 50 at.% Al (vs. Fe-50Al
347 with 760 MPa) [15]. These differences can be explained by deviations in chemical composition
348 (experimentally not verified in Ref. [15]) as outlined above for the high-Al concentration range.

349 Considering the experimental uncertainties in the present study, only the alloys with 30 and 35 at.% Al
350 demonstrate a YS peak. This observation was made despite application of a point defect reducing heat
351 treatment to all alloys that is considered as a pre-requisite for the occurrence of the YS peak. This
352 contradicts earlier reports suggesting the presence of a YS peak up to 47 at.% Al in tension [10,13,15,16]
353 and compression [14]. However, the results presented in Refs. [10,13–16] lack a consistent distinction
354 between σ_y and σ_f . This may lead to recorded temperature-dependent stresses not necessarily only
355 related to the onset of plasticity but involving crack formation and related anomalies of the data.
356 Furthermore, Refs. [10,14–16] do not contain stress-strain and, thus, do not allow for an re-assessment
357 of the onset stresses. Consequently, the assessment of a YS peak necessitates the exclusive consideration
358 of σ_y , as presented in this study employing compression testing and post-deformation microstructural
359 investigations to confirm the activation of plastic deformation, at least to some extent.

360 In contrast to the findings reported in Ref. [53], no decrease in strain hardening is observed in the
361 composition range between 30 and 40 at.% Al in the present study. Instead, a continuous increase in
362 strain hardening is detected, extending up to 53 at.% Al. Ref. [53] employed compression testing, which
363 was terminated at low strains of 2–3 %, and utilized a quasi-static strain rate of $3 \cdot 10^{-4} \text{ s}^{-1}$, similar to
364 10^{-4} s^{-1} used in this investigation. However, the absence of stress–strain curves and lack of information
365 regarding the strain at which the criterion $d\sigma_t/d\varepsilon_t = \sigma_t$ is met, as well as the specification whether the
366 samples failed during testing or not, e.g., by presenting microstructures after deformation, complicate
367 the interpretation of the reported strain hardening values. Specifically the strain hardening right after the

368 onset of plasticity is expected to resemble similar trends as strength. This is indeed the case for the
369 dataset generated in this study when comparing Figure 6b and a with the most pronounced changes for
370 > 42 at.% Al.

371 The post-deformation microstructure observed in the present study, including the formation of kink
372 bands, has previously not been reported in literature for iron aluminides. Kink bands represent a
373 localization of plastic deformation and are observed at temperatures up to 700 °C. Apart from dynamic
374 recovery the appearance of kink bands might contribute to the continuously decreasing strain hardening
375 capability of iron aluminides with increasing temperature. However, deformation bands in general are
376 reported to disappear at elevated temperatures as more slip systems become activated. This enhances
377 homogeneous deformation and localized plastic deformation becomes less [54,59–61]. This is not the
378 case for iron aluminides in the tested composition and temperatures up to 700 °C.

379 After the deformation at 700 °C, the onset of dynamic recrystallization was observed for alloys with
380 < 47 at.% Al, even though these alloys possess lower homologous test temperatures than the ones with
381 higher Al-content. An entirely recrystallized microstructure is expected for larger total strains as
382 reported in Ref. [54]. The absence of dynamic recrystallization for alloys with higher Al contents might
383 be rationalized by the increasing vacancy concentration in *B2*-ordered FeAl [45] and with this, the
384 increasing probability for dynamic recovery by dislocation annihilation rather than recrystallization.
385 Another possible origin is the reduction in grain boundary mobility and therefore retarding
386 recrystallization when atomic ordering becomes more pronounced [54]. As dynamic recrystallization is
387 dependent on total strain and strain rate [54], either of both might be too low to achieve dynamic
388 recrystallization at the temperatures tested.

5. Conclusion

389 Based on the results gained in this study, the following conclusions are drawn:

- 390 1. After the point defect-reducing heat treatment at 400 °C for 120 h, no YS peak was found in the
391 present study for alloys with > 35 at.% Al. In the current study, a well-defined dwell time at the
392 testing temperature was used, leading to different thermal vacancy concentrations prior to
393 starting the test. These concentrations vary depending on Al-concentration and on temperature
394 due to the exponential temperature dependence of the kinetics. Previous reports on the YS peak
395 in literature for higher Al-contents can be explained by several factors, ranging from chemical
396 inhomogeneity, the specific (thermo-)mechanical treatments and the distinct differentiation of
397 σ_f and σ_y .
- 398 2. Kink band formation is the cause for the decreasing strain hardening capability with increasing
399 temperatures in iron aluminides. In general, deformation bands are found to occur at angles
400 close to 45° with respect to the compression direction [59]. The appearances of kink bands found
401 in the present study differ significantly from this angle, which is indicative of a superposition
402 of kink band formation and uniform rotation of grains. Alloys with ≥ 47 at.% Al show low grain
403 boundary strength and are not suitable for being subjected to tensile loads to probe the onset of
404 plastic flow σ_y .

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Conflict of Interest

412 The authors declare no conflict of interest.

Data Availability Statement

413 The data presented in this study are available in Zenodo at <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.17510975>,
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